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Spatial Scenarios With Real-Time Spatial Delphi and Asymptotic Consensus Analysis: An Application to Ten European Coastal Cities

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ABSTRACT

Recent climatic events, such as coastal erosion, floods, and elevated temperatures, threaten the planet’s sustainability and the well-being of European coastal cities. These events are expected to increase significantly, emphasizing the urgent need for careful analysis to inform policy development and prevent dystopian scenarios. In the Futures Studies (FS) context, the development of future scenarios is essential for depicting long-term outcomes and facilitating effective planning, which can be achieved using various methods, including the Real-Time Spatial Delphi. This paper applies to the Delphi-based spatial scenario (DBSS), adopting a novel web-based open platform, to obtain spatial convergence of opinions among a panel of experts using spatial analysis and statistical indicators. The DBSS method was applied to 10 European coastal areas in seven different countries, involving 167 experts to assess climate impacts in 2050. This paper introduces for the first time, the concept of Asymptotic Theoretical Consensus to obtain a deeper understanding of the dynamic process, including duration, smoothness of convergence, and stability. The identified scenarios validate the proposed method and provide significant benefits to stakeholders, policymakers, local authorities, and governmental bodies in formulating efficacious strategies and confronting the challenges presented by climate change.

1 | Introduction

In the last decade, extreme events, including rising temperatures, air pollution, and sudden changes in the weather, have brought greater interest and awareness among institutional bodies and the population (McHugh et al. 2021). According to the United Nations (UN), climate change refers to “*long-term changes in temperature and weather patterns*” (Lilienfeld et al. 2018), establishing a correlation between climate impacts and human activities. Indeed, based on the most recent data presented in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports, the Earth’s temperature has risen by 1.1°C as a

result of human activity (Allan et al. 2021). In the European context, climate change impacts are evident through the occurrence of hazards, such as air pollution, high temperatures, floods, sea level rise, biodiversity loss, coastal erosion, and increased mortality (Kemp et al. 2022). For the IPCC, the negative impacts are already showing in our economy, our health, and our ecosystems (Iacobuță et al. 2022), significantly increasing year after year (Pörtner et al. 2022). Coastal and marine regions in European cities are particularly susceptible to the devastating impacts of climate change; research shows that sea levels could increase by up to 5.0 mm in 2100 (I. P. O. C 2007), resulting in coastal erosion and potential saltwater intrusion

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into the subsoil (Calafat et al. 2022). Furthermore, the surface temperature of European seas has been six times higher over the last 25 years compared to global oceans (Buongiorno Nardelli et al. 2013), leading to different concerns among scientists and decision-making bodies. Given the potentially catastrophic implications of these events, immediate strategies, policies, and measures need to be implemented to mitigate the outcomes of climate change (Berkhout 2013). There is a need for accurate definitions of future events to plan efficient actions in the present and avoid dystopian futures. In the Futures Studies (FS) context, the development of future scenarios can aid in identifying potential opportunities or threats that may emerge in the coming years (Bishop et al. 2007). This, in turn, can help in devising strategies for the present. Scenarios refer to imagined sequences of events that illustrate decision-making points and causal processes; they go beyond mere descriptions and do not aim to predict the future, but to investigate the dynamics and influential factors that shape future outcomes (Greeuw et al. 2000).

In FS, scenarios can be developed in different ways; however, one of the most widely used approaches is the combination of the scenario method with the Delphi method (Linstone and Turoff 1975), forming the so-called Delphi-based scenarios (DBS). The Delphi method was first developed by the RAND Corporation in the 1950s, by Olaf Helmer, Norman Dalkey, and Nicholas Rescher and is composed of several iterative rounds (typically 2–3), administering a questionnaire to a panel of experts to find most of the time (but not exclusively) a consensus or stability (Dajani et al. 1979). Although DBS is an effective tool for collecting opinions from a group of experts, it has certain drawbacks, including the time-consuming nature, the experts' engagement, and the facilitator's efforts in the process (Calleo and Pilla 2023). Nevertheless, in the context of climate change, the main limitation of DBS is the absence of spatial references in the process (Di Zio and Pacinelli 2011). Over the years, two different innovations have been proposed by Di Zio and Pacinelli (2011) and Di Zio et al. (2017), namely the Spatial Delphi (SD) and the Real-Time Spatial Delphi (RTSD), two new versions of the classical Delphi, which include geographical aspects. However, from the first applications, both methods remained unexplored due to the following reasons: (a) Spatial Delphi: similar to the Delphi method, requires strong efforts from the facilitator, for the intensive time-consuming nature of the process and the challenges involved in summarizing the results in a statistical form. (b) Real-Time Spatial Delphi: requires proficiency in programming for developing Web-GIS systems and designing new surveys. Furthermore, the main drawback is the lack of a specialized system where the original archetype introduced by Di Zio et al. (2017) is no longer accessible, thus preventing further investigations.

In recent years, to overcome this limitation, several developments have emerged in the use of the Real-Time Spatial Delphi within the field of Futures Studies. Notably, Calleo et al. (2023) applied the method to develop spatial scenarios in the climate change context for the city of Dublin in 2050. Moreover, other studies in the environmental domain have employed the Real-Time Spatial Delphi to construct spatial scenarios (e.g., Giuffrida et al. 2024; Calleo et al. 2025). However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, there are no contributions that validate

this methodology through comparative analysis across multiple case studies. Finally, given the “roundless” nature of the process, there are currently no clearly established indicators for concluding the survey, which may introduce potential biases in determining its endpoint.

To address these challenges, we consider for this application the use of “Real-Time Geo-Spatial Consensus System” (RT-GSCS, <http://www.rtgscs.com/>), a new and innovative web-based open platform useful for the development of Delphi-based spatial scenarios (DBSS) (Calleo et al. 2023). The platform adopts a real-time iterative approach typical of the Spatial Delphi and Real-Time Spatial Delphi to reach a consensus among a panel of experts (Calleo and Pilla 2024). The tool is highly valuable in situations that require making informed decisions and predictions, enabling privileged witnesses to offer their opinions and perspectives on spatial issues. In this paper, RT-GSCS is adopted to illustrate a European case study to identify potential impacts of climate change in 2050. Specifically, it focuses on 10 European coastal areas, which are part of the “Smart control of the climate resilience in European coastal cities” (SCORE H2020) project. The areas identified are Benidorm, Dublin, Gdansk, Massa, Oeiras, Piran, Samsun, San Sebastián, Sligo, and Vilanova i la Geltrú. The main innovation of this study is the use of the RTSD to develop climate scenarios (better defined as DBSS), adopting spatial analysis and consensus modeling. Furthermore, we introduce for the first time in Delphi processes the concept of Asymptotic Theoretical Consensus (ATC) to obtain a deeper understanding of the process's dynamics, including duration, smoothness of convergence, and stability.

Specifically, the main research objectives are:

1. *RO*₁: To propose a robust methodology to conduct a Real-Time Spatial Delphi process through the development of a novel application incorporating multiple case studies, thus allowing comparability.
2. *RO*₂: To provide an overview of the projected climate impacts in multiple cities across various European countries in 2050, employing participatory methods, innovative algorithms, spatial analysis, and consensus modeling.
3. *RO*₃: To compile an updated list of strengths and weaknesses of the Real-Time Spatial Delphi derived from the large case study.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. This section serves as an introduction to the study, delineating the problem statement while also highlighting the primary innovations. In Section 2, we elucidate the materials and methods employed in our research, while Section 3 delves into the ultimate findings and ensuing discussion. Lastly, in Section 4, we provide insights into the conclusions and future directions.

2 | Delphi-Based Spatial Scenarios

2.1 | Research Design

In this section, we illustrate the methodology adopted for the development of DBSS. DBSS are a novel concept in the family of

FIGURE 1 | Delphi-based spatial scenario method.

the Delphi, which combines Delphi-based scenarios and Real-Time Spatial Delphi (Calleo et al. 2023). To pursue the aim of this paper, we use “Real-Time Geo-Spatial Consensus System” (RT-GSCS, www.rtgscs.com), a novel web-based open platform adopting the Real-Time Spatial Delphi algorithm (Di Zio et al. 2017) to obtain a spatial convergence of opinions among a panel of experts. We apply the method to assess the impacts of climate change on 10 European coastal areas in 7 different countries in 2050. The main aim is to identify narrow areas of the occurrence of climate phenomena to develop local strategies in the present evaluating the potential of the method. Our method can be defined as a modified DBS, drawing inspiration from the Strategic Foresight approach suggested by Bishop et al. (2007). The six steps, integrated with the Real-Time Spatial Delphi method, include: (1) Framing, (2) Scanning, (3) Forecasting, (4) Visioning, (5) Planning, and (6) Acting. A depiction of the method adopted in this paper is provided in Figure 1.

The initial step of our method involves the development of a robust research design, where we evaluate various components, considering their potential positive or negative effects on the final results (e.g., time horizon, panelists). During this phase, we define 2050 as a time horizon for our investigation, outline the working environment, and establish the methodology that will guide all our processes (Figure 1). We decided to set the time horizon in 2050 because it is advisable to select a time frame that offers significance for decision-making while still remaining within the bounds of practicality for making plausible forecasts (Kosow and Gaßner 2008), in line with other contribution related with climate change (i.e., UN and EU). Since our aim is to investigate climate impacts in 2050 by identifying the areas with a high plausibility of effect, we

consider the challenges and risks of the different cities through an analysis of the literature, consultation of stakeholders, and data available.

The cities under investigation are facing multiple challenges as an effect of climate change, including flood risks, coastal erosion, and extreme weather events, including heavy precipitations, sea level rise, and high temperatures. Finally, taking into consideration the use of RT-GSCS, we started to test the platform with a group of experts from the Spatial Dynamics Lab at University College Dublin to gather feedback and address any possible concerns (e.g., issues, bugs, typos).

2.2 | Key Drivers and Proposed Questions

Once we have a complete framework of our study, including the territorial boundaries, time horizon, and supplementary material (i.e., guidelines, spatial maps, project reports), we proceed to identify a draft list of key drivers (*K*). In this study, we assume the key drivers as the impacts of climate change currently ongoing in the areas under study. To determine the key drivers, we conduct desk research aimed at analyzing available data (such as spatial data, a corpus of documents, and pre-existent works acquired), to have a draft list of plausible impacts. Usually, in the Delphi method, workshops are organized to formulate a draft list of projections for key drivers, refining them with experts until a shortened list is available. In our case, we have a different perspective, in fact, the main key drivers are already available in the WP1 (literature review and policy analysis) and WP2 (living lab workshops con stakeholders) of the SCORE EU project. This is extremely useful to

TABLE 1 | Research questions.

Area	Research questions		
	<i>RQ</i> ₁	<i>RQ</i> ₂	<i>RQ</i> ₃
Benidorm	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will be most affected by high temperatures?	What area will be most at risk of flooding?
Dublin	What area will be most at risk of flooding?	What area will be most at risk of erosion?	What area will be most affected by extreme events?
Gdansk	What area will have the greatest impact on the rising sea?	What area will be most affected by extreme events?	What area will be most at risk of flooding?
Massa	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will be most at risk of flooding?	What area will be most at risk of erosion?
Oeiras	What area will be most affected by high temperatures?	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will have the greatest impact on the rising sea?
Piran	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will be most affected by high temperatures?	What area will be most affected by extreme events?
Samsun	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will be most at risk of flooding?	What area will be most at risk of erosion?
San Sebastián	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will be most at risk of erosion?	What area will be most affected by high temperatures?
Sligo	What area will be most at risk of erosion?	In what area will biodiversity be most threatened?	What area will be most at risk of flooding?
Vilanova i la Geltrú	What area will be most at risk of erosion?	What area will be most at risk of flooding?	What area will have the greatest impact on the rising sea?

speed up the procedure since the drivers are already identified, refined, and validated by a panel of experts with a high degree of expertise in the field (including academics, researchers, company members, and local authorities). Once we have a draft list of drivers, we consider for each area the first three plausible impacts based on the highest percentage of agreement among experts regarding their perceived importance.

The choice to extract the first three impacts is entirely subjective and stems from the research team's aim to avoid potential dropouts by experts during the process related to high amounts of questions (i.e., all impacts for all the cities). However, the approach is flexible to changes and/or modifications in relation to the research objectives. It is possible to highlight the common concerns for the different areas, including coastal erosion, flood risk, sea level rise, biodiversity loss, high temperature, and extreme events. Following what is described in the project proposal, these drivers are extremely dangerous and can lead to important challenges, including damage to commercial and residential buildings, tourism loss, human health problems, and transport issues.

In summary, we extracted $K = 30$ drivers, 3 for each city, resulting in 30 different “spatial” research questions. Once we obtain the full list of drivers, the next step involves formulating the Delphi questions to then be presented to the panel through the digital platform. The research questions are formulated with an emphasis on clarity and comprehensibility, aiming to prevent potential issues throughout the process. In fact, we consider three main dimensions before drafting the questions: (1) time horizon, (2) drivers, and (3) geographical area.

At this point, we obtain a set of questions composed of the three previous dimensions for each driver and each city (e.g., “Thinking about 2050... what area will be most at risk of coastal erosion in Dublin?”). Before uploading to the platform, the research team proceeds to validate them in terms of clarity and consistency resulting in minimal changes regarding syntax. The final questions (Table 1) are subsequently uploaded to the platform, associated with the corresponding geographic coordinates (x, y). To simplify the process, the questions are well organized in the platform, divided for each topic and each geographic region, this is because the experts can provide relevant judgments based on their expertise or location avoiding any confusion derived from the technical usage of the platform.

2.3 | Panel of Experts

In this phase, we select a panel of experts for our Real-Time Spatial Delphi survey. There is no consensus in the literature for the best sample (in terms of numerosity and expertise) to be considered; however, the conditions of a multidisciplinary panel of experts, composed of individuals with various types of expertise, should be satisfied (Baker et al. 2006).

In this case, since we have multiple areas in different countries, we decided to consider two types of experts in our panel: (1) Internal panelists: we engaged individuals highly skilled in environmental and climate issues who are also part of the SCORE H2020 project. This choice is based on the fact that internal experts possess not only expertise in the subject matter but also a comprehensive understanding of the project itself.

TABLE 2 | Panelists involved.

Area	Contacted panelists		Total	Participating panelists		Total
	Internal	External		Internal	External	
Benidorm	5	23	28	2	12	14
Dublin	12	50	62	6	20	26
Gdansk	4	25	29	1	15	16
Massa	8	20	28	1	10	11
Oeiras	3	22	25	2	18	20
Piran	5	20	25	2	13	15
Samsun	3	14	17	1	11	12
San Sebastián	3	28	31	2	13	15
Sligo	9	15	24	3	13	16
Vilanova i la Geltrú	8	43	51	3	19	22
Total	60	260	320	23	144	167

Note: Bold values pertain to the total of columns and rows.

(2) External panelists: we invite an external panel of experts with appropriate competencies in the field of study. This choice aims to form a robust panel with diverse expertise, encompassing academic scholars, stakeholders, and representatives from companies, NGOs, and local government bodies. In fact, we want to distinguish the viewpoints of internal experts from those of external individuals who are unacquainted with the project dynamics and remain unaffected by them. Once the experts have been identified (Table 2), we send an email introducing the project and outlining the research objectives, asking for their participation and containing technical information, deadlines, guidelines, and platform instructions. From a first overview, it is possible to note that—as always happens in the Delphi studies—the contacted panelists are more than the participating panelists (in this study, we define “participating panelists”, who have made an action in the platform, in the form of at least one response). Regarding internal experts, out of the 60 contacted, only 23 participated in the study (38%). In contrast, among the 260 external panelists contacted, 144 took part in the study (55%), for a total number of $E = 167$ experts.

2.4 | Survey Administration and Statistical Indicators

The platform adopted for this study is the Real-Time Geo-Spatial Consensus System (v2.0) (www.rtgscs.com). In its current state, the platform enables users to create and manage different surveys and can be employed to achieve a spatial consensus in different contexts, including decision-making and forecasting (Calleo et al. 2023). After preparing the survey for administration (for an extensive review on how to conduct the survey see Calleo and Pilla 2024 or visit <https://www.rtgscs.com/faq/>), the selected experts in the study received a link for access. The RT-GSCS system adopts a role-based architecture to ensure secure and efficient management of spatial surveys, comprising three main user roles: administrators, contributors, and users, each with distinct privileges and responsibilities. (1) Administrators occupy the highest level in the system hierarchy. They are responsible for maintaining the platform

and have full access rights, including control panel operations and the ability to modify source files and code. Their role is essential for ensuring system stability, overseeing user management, and authorizing survey deployment. (2) Contributors are authorized to design and manage spatial surveys, but only after receiving explicit access from administrators. Once permission is granted, contributors can upload an introductory section, formulate survey questions with spatial (x, y) references, and attach relevant supporting materials such as technical documents or datasets. They are also allowed to review spatial responses and access descriptive statistical summaries (Figure 2). However, they are restricted from accessing or modifying system-level files and configurations. (3) Users interact with the system primarily through the user interface. They can respond to survey questions, navigate the interactive map, and view outputs including convergence areas, opinion markers, statistical summaries, and spatial or textual analyses. Users do not have access to contributor-specific functionalities such as survey settings or any personal or identifying information related to other participants.

They can use this link to enter their own information and credentials. In this process, the survey administrator retains the authority to accept, reject, or remove experts as needed, ensuring protection against potential intrusion by external parties. The survey, defined here as a “spatial survey,” is provided by an interactive map, which displays all necessary information in a left-hand sidebar (see Figure 3). Within the sidebar, experts can access the attachments section, which allows them to review the documents preloaded by the research team. These documents provide insight into the ongoing research context, potential guidelines, and any relevant updates concerning the session, similar to the Delphi method. This implementation facilitates the immediate acquisition of existing literature without the use of messages, emails, or communications that would lead experts to spend more effort and time. In the left-hand sidebar, an introduction to the questions is displayed, thus providing the experts with a general research framework. In this case: “Thinking about 2050...,” precede the bar with all the research questions. The experts, based on their degree of expertise and location, can select a question by adding their own

Create New Question

Name

Description

Description

Coordinates(lat,lng)

List of Existing Spatial Questions

Show entries Search:

Name	Coords	Description	Answer Label	Update	Del
Which area of Dublin will be most affected by flooding?	53.3498, -6.2603	<input type="text"/>	Please select the plausibility of	<input type="button" value="Update"/>	<input type="button" value="Delete"/>

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries Previous Next

FIGURE 2 | Question uploading.

FIGURE 3 | System interface.

judgments to the map by inserting one or more opinion-points (Di Zio and Pacinelli 2011). At this point, when an expert places a new opinion-point, an automatic window appears, asking the expert to weigh the plausibility of the judgment on a scale of 1–5 (where 1 is for min plausibility and 5 is for max plausibility). This assessment is conducted to acquire more information about the spatial distribution of the answers and to facilitate subsequent post-GIS analysis (e.g., identification of hotspots on the territory).

From the first point placed, they can see a geometric element represented by a circle on the interactive map. This circle is

representative of the spatial consensus achieved on the territory similar to the interquartile range used in the Delphi method and moves and changes size according to the opinions (namely points) provided by the experts (for an extensive review of the computational algorithm see Calleo and Pilla 2024). During the survey, experts can consult in real-time the size of the circle in km² on the sidebar, thus obtaining a preliminary real-time statistical summary. As the circle becomes smaller, the level of consensus achieved up to that point increases.

The circle of convergence is determined in real-time adopting a statistical algorithm proposed by Di Zio and Pacinelli (2011) and

implemented in the platform (Calleo et al. 2023). Following this logic, the spatial consensus is obtained by adopting a geometric element represented by a circle C , the smallest one among the possible circles containing half of the opinion-points. Similar to the *IQR* adopted in the Delphi method, C includes 50% of the N judgments composed of x, y coordinates. If we assume that at a given moment during the survey, $N = n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_N$, is the distribution of points on the map, the algorithm finds a minimum area A_i of a circle C_i covering half of the points:

$$A_i \supseteq T_{N/2} \quad (1)$$

where $T_{N/2}$ denotes a set of 50% of the N points. Following this logic, since there are infinite possible circles calculated, we impose the constraint that C_i must have the center in one of the N points. At the end, the algorithm calculates for each question an ordered vector $A = A_1, A_2, A_3, \dots, A_N$, where A_i represents the area of a circle centered on point n_i and containing 50% of the N points. Finally, $\min(A)$ corresponds to the spatial consensus achieved on the territory. This logic is implemented to facilitate a convergence of opinions, taking into consideration the possibility that some points may be located in geographic places irrelevant to the research context (e.g., points placed outside the boundaries of the reference city).

During the survey, experts are provided with the opportunity to comment on the judgments of other experts by anonymously inserting textual input on spatial points. Furthermore, when a point is placed outside the geo-consensus circle, an automatic window appears, asking for justification and marking the comment with a red alert flag. This is implemented to ensure that experts have the chance to recognize points and comments outside the consensus, so potentially trigger an anonymous debate and, possibly, revise their judgments, like in classical Delphi.

From the survey, we obtained two main results: (1) geographical (i.e., spatial points, assessments, circle size over the days, etc.) and (2) non-geographical (i.e., rationales provided by experts). The geographical results are exactly the final circle for each question, which encompasses $N/2$ of the total cloud of points given by the experts at the end of the survey, easily comprehensible and valuable through the map without any further processing. Nevertheless, a graphical representation would not provide sufficient elements of analysis for presenting the final results. To overcome this challenge, in this paragraph, we consider the non-geographical results, or the data obtained essentially to measure spatial consensus adopting three main indicators: M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 (Di Zio and Pacinelli 2011).

The first indicator adopted is

$$M_1 = FC \text{ (km}^2\text{)} \quad (2)$$

where FC represents the area of the final circle achieved in km^2 . However, this indicator is an absolute value that does not consider the size of the study area and the initial size of the circle, making it inadequate for assessing spatial consensus. To address this challenge, we also utilize a second indicator

calculating the ratio between the final circle's area (FC) and city's surface area (S):

$$M_2 = 1 - \frac{FC}{S} \quad (3)$$

The degree of geo-consensus is reflected by this indicator, where a measure closer to 1 indicates a smaller circle in comparison to the surface. This indicates a convergence of opinions achieved on the territory.

In addition to the previous indicators, we adopt another indicator to gain insight into the dynamic process of spatial convergence during the analysis:

$$M_3 = \frac{FC}{IC} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

In this case, M_3 is used as a measure of the degree of consensus and is expressed as a percentage, by calculating the ratio between the final circle area (FC) and the initial circle area (IC). Here, it is important to emphasize that the initial area of the circle is not determined by the first expert, but rather by the second point inserted. This is because the statistical algorithm cannot be employed with only one point (indeed, the first circle is set a priori as $C = 50 \text{ km}^2$). For this indicator, the higher the value (close to 100%) the lower the convergence of opinions among the participants; the closer the value to zero, the higher the achieved convergence.

Finally, consensus cannot be assumed as the only stopping criterion, in fact, according to von Der Gracht (2012), a crucial aspect to be considered is the stability of the group responses when “the results of two consecutive rounds are not significantly different.” Since our process is considered “roundless” (Gordon and Pease 2006), we evaluate the stability of non-geographical results (such as time and dates). In our study, we allocate a maximum working period of 30 days to the experts. Of these, 20 days were provided for their unrestricted work (without sending any email to them), while the remaining 10 days were designated for achieving stability in the process. Indeed, after 20 days, we proceed by sending a final email to request validation of the scenarios, inviting experts to conduct a comprehensive review and verification of the scenarios. They are encouraged to contribute novel insights and provide explanations if their responses diverge from the geo-consensus circle. This is because we give the experts the last opportunity to validate the scenarios before closing the exercise. This step necessitates revisiting the platform, closely examining the region where responses were concentrated, and either identifying a new area within the circle or offering a rationale for selecting a location outside the circle. Alternatively, experts can affirm that they do not identify any new significant areas. In summary, in our context, stability is attained when, during the final 10 days, the size of the circle either decreases or remains relatively constant.

After completing the exercise, we obtain a final distribution of days associated with circle size areas, and we can conduct various analyses, including time series modeling. For our study,

we adopt three different exponential models implemented on MATLAB, denoted as

$$Y = b \cdot \exp(-x \cdot c) + d \quad (5)$$

$$Y = b \cdot \exp(-x) + d \quad (6)$$

$$Y = b \cdot \exp(-x \cdot c) \quad (7)$$

where Y represents the dependent variable, x the independent variable and b , c , and d are the parameters of the model estimated to fit the model to the data. In this case, for each scenario, we conduct an analysis of the three models, assessing their goodness of fit by evaluating the R^2 (see Appendix) and selecting the most suitable model. Moreover – as described above – in this paper we adopted a subjective criterion to stop the survey, and for this reason, to investigate further the convergence process and the stability achieved, we introduce the concept of “Asymptotic Theoretical Consensus (ATC),” denoted as:

$$ATC = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x) \quad (8)$$

where $f(x)$ represents the best estimated exponential function of the circle size at time x . The ATC is calculated as the horizontal asymptote of the estimated curve. This provides deeper insights into the behavior of the survey over an extended period and is rooted in the assumption that the survey continues infinitely, allowing us to explore the limits and stability of the circle size in this hypothetical scenario. In this case, the results can be analyzed following three main assumptions: if the last inserted points are close to the horizontal asymptote, we can successfully consider achieved a convergence. If $ATC = 0$, yet the final data points are significantly distant from zero, it suggests that extending the survey for a longer period may lead to achieving convergence. However, when $ATC \neq 0$, it suggests that persisting with the survey would likely be futile since we would presumably not achieve a circle size lower than that threshold. Overall, the main opportunity of this analysis is to better understand the convergence process and project this progression forward.

In this paper, for a correct representation and visualization of the final results, we import the matrices with the attached spatial coordinates, weights, and other information in the ArcGIS PRO software. Specifically, for the analysis of the final results we generated satellite images inclusive of opinion-points expressed by the experts and the final circle area resulted in the spatial consensus. Furthermore, since we have for each judgment a weight $w = 1 - 5$ denoting the plausibility of the impact in 2050, to visualize the density of the phenomenon in the territory, we adopt a heat map analysis based on the weight assigned by the experts. The heatmap is adapted to visualize the spatial distribution of the weight to identify hotspots or areas of concentrated high values, as well as cold spots or areas with low values.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Spatial Results and Heat Maps

In this study, the aim was to validate the RTSD method, examining the potential climate-related risks that European

coastal cities may face by the year 2050. We utilized the RT-GSCS platform to analyze and develop three main scenarios for each city in the research areas of Table 1. Throughout this period, we achieved a significant level of convergence by successfully addressing all the queries posed on the platform. Of the 320 experts contacted for the survey, $E = 167$ agreed to participate and shared their assessments by marking at least one point on the map. The results arising from the collaborative efforts of the experts are presented and discussed in this section, starting from Figure 4.

The spatial analysis conducted in this study highlights the pressing and multifaceted challenges European coastal cities face due to climate change, offering insights into the geographical distribution of vulnerabilities and potential mitigation strategies. This section discusses the broader implications of the results, emphasizing common trends, critical disparities among cities, and recommendations for future action. Across the analyzed cities, flooding and coastal erosion emerged as the most recurrent risks, underscoring the widespread vulnerability of coastal areas to rising sea levels and extreme weather events. Urban centers, such as Dublin and Gdańsk, are particularly susceptible due to their dense infrastructure and economic reliance on coastal zones. Experts consistently recommended nature-based solutions (NBS), such as dune restoration and vegetation enhancement, as effective mitigation measures (see Figure 4). However, the effectiveness of these strategies requires early implementation and sustained maintenance. Another shared concern is the threat of high temperatures in urban cores, as identified in Benidorm, Oeiras, and San Sebastián.

Urban heat islands, exacerbated by insufficient vegetation and high population density, pose significant risks to public health and energy systems. Proposed interventions, including the expansion of urban green spaces and improved tree maintenance, align with broader climate resilience goals but necessitate significant policy and resource investments. Despite these shared vulnerabilities, each city exhibits unique risk profiles shaped by local geography, climate, and socioeconomic factors. For instance, Dublin faces compounded risks from coastal erosion, flooding, and extreme events, with critical infrastructure such as train lines and water pumping stations at risk. These findings call for integrated urban planning that prioritizes climate resilience. Massa is particularly threatened by biodiversity loss due to coastal erosion and eutrophication, highlighting the need for targeted measures to protect marine ecosystems and tourism-dependent economies. Piran stands out for its susceptibility to biodiversity loss in key coastal habitats, emphasizing the importance of preserving marine protected areas and restoring mangroves. Sligo and Vilanova i la Geltrú face erosion and flooding risks that threaten both residential areas and infrastructure, necessitating proactive water management and coastal defense systems. The findings underline the critical importance of integrating spatial data into climate adaptation strategies, thus demonstrating the validity of the method in complex contexts. The ability to pinpoint specific high-risk areas allows policymakers to prioritize interventions and allocate resources effectively. However, achieving consensus on mitigation measures remains a challenge, as highlighted by the variability in expert responses and the presence of multiple clusters in certain scenarios. This underscores the need for

FIGURE 4 | Spatial results.

FIGURE 5 | Heatmaps of the plausibility (blue = min and yellow = max).

participatory approaches that involve diverse stakeholders, including local communities, to balance scientific recommendations with socioeconomic realities. The spatial distribution of expert-identified data points, weighted by plausibility, reveals critical patterns that underscore the utility of integrating geographical and statistical insights in climate risk assessments.

The distribution of data points provides a nuanced view of how experts perceive vulnerabilities across different cities and scenarios (Figure 5). The weighted plausibility assigned to each point highlights areas of heightened concern, allowing for the identification of priority zones where mitigation efforts should be focused. Dublin's flood-prone zones along the River Liffey

and the city's eastern coastal areas consistently received high weights, indicating strong agreement among experts about the urgency of addressing these risks. In Benidorm, the distribution of high-weight points near Mal Pas Beach and the West Beach reinforces the need for ecosystem-based interventions to combat biodiversity loss and flooding risks. Gdańsk demonstrated a more dispersed spatial pattern, particularly in scenarios addressing extreme events, reflecting the city's complex interplay of risks tied to port infrastructure and rising sea levels. The inclusion of expert-assigned weights enhances the interpretative depth of the spatial analysis, allowing for the differentiation between areas of perceived low and high plausibility. In cities like Oeiras and San Sebastián, this weighting mechanism was instrumental in delineating subtle risk gradients within relatively small study areas.

However, the variability in weights across cities suggests differences in how experts perceive the severity and likelihood of risks, potentially influenced by their domain expertise and familiarity with local contexts. The clustering of data points, particularly in scenarios with multiple high-weight zones, highlights the challenges of reaching spatial consensus. Cities like Sligo and Vilanova i la Geltrú exhibited fragmented distributions, with experts identifying multiple plausible areas for interventions. This fragmentation underscores the need for iterative deliberation processes and advanced analytical techniques, such as fuzzy clustering, to accommodate diverse expert perspectives. The spatial distributions provide actionable insights for policymakers by identifying critical areas that require immediate attention. The integration of weighted plausibility data into urban planning frameworks enables the prioritization of interventions in high-risk zones, such as Dublin's central flood-prone areas or Benidorm's biodiversity hotspots. Furthermore, the approach can guide the allocation of resources for infrastructure improvements, ecosystem restoration, and emergency response planning. However, the variability in expert weights and the presence of multiple clusters suggest that policy decisions should account for uncertainties and involve a broader stakeholder base to ensure the inclusivity and acceptability of proposed solutions. The weighting system also presents an opportunity for future research to explore the incorporation of dynamic weights that evolve based on real-time data inputs or expert feedback during extended deliberations.

3.2 | Statistical Indicators and Time Series Analysis

The previous analysis highlighted the dynamic nature of geographical convergence across diverse areas and scenarios. In this case, by examining the convergence indicators M_1 , M_2 , and M_3 we obtained a detailed understanding of the consensus-building process among experts. Despite variations in study areas and initial conditions, the results reveal consistent patterns and valuable insights into the factors influencing spatial consensus (Table 3).

A notable achievement across the study is the significant reduction in the initial circle (*IC*) size for most scenarios, as reflected in M_1 . This reduction demonstrates the experts' ability to converge on specific portions of the territory, even in

complex spatial contexts. However, the level of convergence, as measured by M_3 , varies across scenarios and areas. For instance, the city of Dublin exhibited strong convergence, with M_3 values consistently below the 20% threshold, supporting the notion of effective collaboration. Conversely, areas such as Oeiras and specific scenarios in Benidorm highlight challenges, including the presence of multiple clusters and the inherent difficulty of reaching consensus in smaller or highly segmented territories. The second indicator, M_2 , consistently demonstrated values close to 1 across scenarios and regions, signaling strong spatial consensus. However, nuances emerged, particularly in smaller areas like Oeiras, where lower M_2 values suggest that achieving consensus in confined spaces can be more demanding. This observation underscores the complexity of aligning expert opinions when territories are narrowly defined or fragmented. The third indicator, M_3 , provided critical insights into the role of clustering and divergence among expert opinions. For example, while cities such as Gdansk and Piran achieved M_3 values below 10%, indicative of robust collaboration, other areas, including scenarios in Benidorm and Oeiras, exhibited higher M_3 values.

These results align with the hypothesis that the presence of multiple clusters, often stemming from diverse expert perspectives, can hinder convergence. Despite these challenges, even scenarios with marginally higher M_3 values often demonstrate meaningful consensus within specific segments of the territory. The findings also reveal a broader trend: spatial consensus is influenced by a combination of geographical characteristics, the extent of the study area, and the diversity of expert knowledge. In expansive regions like Gdansk, the convergence process benefited from a larger study area, where clustering had less impact. In contrast, smaller areas, such as Oeiras, amplified the difficulty of identifying shared zones, as evidenced by higher M_3 values and modest M_2 scores. Furthermore, the roundness nature of the Real-Time Spatial Delphi methodology provided unique insights into the evolution of consensus over time. Historical data enabled the modeling of expert interactions and convergence dynamics, shedding light on aspects such as the smoothness and stability of the process. These temporal analyses revealed that areas with more cohesive clusters, such as San Sebastián, exhibited faster convergence, whereas regions with greater variability in opinion required more time and effort to stabilize. Ultimately, this study underscores the strengths and limitations of the RTSD methodology. The indicators proved effective in capturing different dimensions of convergence, offering a robust framework for evaluating spatial consensus. However, the presence of multiple clusters and the scale of the study area emerged as critical challenges. These findings emphasize the importance of tailoring methodologies to account for geographical and contextual complexities, ensuring the effectiveness of participatory spatial processes.

Moreover, the time series analysis (Figure 6) revealed notable insights into the dynamics of consensus-building across the studied cities and scenarios, utilizing exponential models to quantify convergence patterns. Stability in responses, as measured by the decrease on average circle size, was achieved in most scenarios within 10–15 days, significantly outpacing the traditional Delphi process, which typically requires 2–3 months to reach similar outcomes (Calleo et al. 2023). However, specific conditions, such as those in Dublin, extended the stabilization

TABLE 3 | Statistical indicators.

Area	Scenario	Study area (km ²)	Initial circle (km ²)	Final circle			Points	Comments
				(km ²)	M_1	M_2		
Benidorm	S1	38.51	0.89	0.36	0.990	40.45	25	8
Benidorm	S2	38.51	1.59	0.21	0.994	13.21	18	3
Benidorm	S3	38.51	2.30	0.10	0.997	4.35	21	7
Dublin	S1	117.8	8.24	0.77	0.993	9.34	58	13
Dublin	S2	117.8	3.25	0.15	0.999	4.61	54	16
Dublin	S3	117.8	2.92	0.54	0.995	18.49	50	11
Gdansk	S1	263.4	5.65	0.22	0.999	3.89	20	4
Gdansk	S2	263.4	6.32	0.38	0.998	6.01	25	9
Gdansk	S3	263.4	4.32	0.14	0.999	3.24	27	6
Massa	S1	94	7.46	0.23	0.997	3.08	18	2
Massa	S2	94	10.32	1.08	0.988	10.47	22	3
Massa	S3	94	2.37	0.19	0.998	8.02	19	5
Oeiras	S1	6.63	1.73	0.35	0.947	20.23	28	9
Oeiras	S2	6.63	1.20	0.21	0.968	17.50	26	7
Oeiras	S3	6.63	3.86	0.15	0.977	3.88	23	3
Piran	S1	44	4.30	0.10	0.997	2.09	24	23
Piran	S2	44	3.78	0.12	0.997	2.65	27	22
Piran	S3	44	7.61	0.11	0.997	1.45	31	27
Samsun	S1	51	5.36	0.15	0.997	2.79	20	17
Samsun	S2	51	8.92	0.23	0.995	2.58	19	18
Samsun	S3	51	7.21	0.13	0.997	1.80	23	23
San Sebastián	S1	60.89	1.56	0.12	0.998	7.69	20	8
San Sebastián	S2	60.89	0.95	0.13	0.997	13.68	21	5
San Sebastián	S3	60.89	1.58	0.24	0.996	15.19	24	8
Sligo	S1	10.3	7.11	0.23	0.977	3.24	24	11
Sligo	S2	10.3	1.76	0.12	0.988	6.82	19	7
Sligo	S3	10.3	5.02	0.22	0.978	4.38	22	9
Vilanova i la Geltrú	S1	34	2.76	0.33	0.996	11.96	29	6
Vilanova i la Geltrú	S2	34	2.86	0.51	0.995	17.83	24	4
Vilanova i la Geltrú	S3	34	3.35	0.50	0.995	14.93	29	5
Total							790	299

period to approximately 30 days, highlighting the influence of contextual and regional factors on the consensus-building process. Across all cities, the early days of the survey exhibited considerable fluctuations in circle size, reflecting the natural variability in initial expert responses. These fluctuations diminished rapidly, particularly by the 10th to 13th day, as experts engaged iteratively with the evolving spatial consensus. For the majority of scenarios, stabilization occurred within a 10- to 15-day timeframe, indicating a rapid convergence of expert opinions. This trend underscores the effectiveness of the Real-Time Delphi process in fostering timely consensus. However, in specific scenarios, such as those in Dublin, consensus-building required up to 30 days. This deviation may be attributed to the complexity of the scenario or variability in expert engagement.

To capture the stabilization patterns quantitatively, three exponential models were applied to each scenario, with the most suitable model selected based on R^2 values and ATC metrics. Across most scenarios, Model 1 (a simple exponential decay model) consistently outperformed the other models, demonstrating R^2 values exceeding 0.7 in over 80% of cases. This indicates that the convergence process typically follows a smooth, monotonic trajectory toward stability. Scenarios with ATC values nearing zero correlated strongly with high R^2 values, further validating the suitability of the selected models. This relationship suggests that as the circle size stabilizes, temporal variability in expert responses diminishes. The city's extended stabilization period (up to 30 days in some scenarios) reflects unique challenges in achieving spatial consensus. High

FIGURE 6 | Time series analysis.

ATC values during the first 15 days indicate persistent fluctuations in expert responses, possibly due to the diversity of expert perspectives or the complexity of the geographic context. In scenarios such as Massa's Sc. 1, higher ATC values in the early phase suggest a need for prolonged engagement. However, the circle size plateaued after approximately 12 days, indicating that further iterations would likely yield minimal additional convergence. In scenarios with pronounced early fluctuations or where additional points were introduced mid-survey, the stabilization period extended slightly. These trends were evident in the corresponding R^2 values and the delayed plateauing of circle size. Notably, scenarios with higher initial variability tended to converge more effectively when sufficient time was provided for iterative expert interaction. The methodology enabled rapid convergence compared to traditional Delphi approaches, demonstrating its applicability for time-sensitive spatial planning and consensus-building exercises. The applied models effectively captured diverse stabilization patterns across cities, with Model 1 emerging as the most robust across the majority of scenarios.

The extended stabilization in Dublin and similar cases highlights the importance of accounting for regional and scenario-specific complexities in the survey design and interpretation of results. The analysis confirms the effectiveness of Real-Time Delphi methods, supported by exponential modeling, in fostering rapid and reliable consensus across diverse urban scenarios. While the majority of scenarios achieved stabilization within 2 weeks, exceptions such as Dublin emphasize the need for flexibility in survey timelines to accommodate contextual challenges. The application of exponential models, validated by high R^2 values and ATC metrics, provides a rigorous framework for analyzing spatial consensus dynamics. This study contributes to the understanding of temporal patterns in

consensus-building processes and demonstrates the utility of advanced modeling techniques in participatory spatial planning.

3.3 | Updated Strengths and Weaknesses

From the results emerged, this section allows us to present a comprehensive discussion. This discussion highlights a revised compilation of the method's advantages and drawbacks (Table 4) when contrasted with the approach put forth by Di Zio et al. (2017); Calleo et al. (2023); Giuffrida et al. (2024); Calleo et al. (2024); Calleo et al. (2025). In our study, the efficacy of the Real-Time Spatial Delphi technique becomes evident as a method to develop DBSS, thus promoting comparability. DBSS encompass a critical component of our study, useful for various research contexts and domains, specifically when there are spatial elements involved. Nevertheless, it is imperative to emphasize a significant aspect. In DBSS, all elements must be taken into consideration. This is particularly pertinent as the future becomes increasingly uncertain, especially when dealing with territorial matters subject to rapid temporal trends. Specifically, in defining the concept of DBSS in this paper, our primary output refers to maps containing N points and the convergence circle C . However, this representation cannot be the sole basis for present-day actions. DBSS encompasses a wide array of associated information, including ATC, the quality of the consensus-building process, indicators, stability metrics, and, notably, expert-written comments. All of these pieces of information constitute a practical framework that delineates the entire application context without omitting any elements. Such a framework proves immensely valuable for shaping proactive policies within the geographical domain.

TABLE 4 | Updated strengths and weaknesses of the Real-Time Spatial Delphi.

	Technological functionality	Methodological considerations
Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A designed user-friendly interface Effortless response process A cost-effective system Creation of multiple surveys supported Real-time response capabilities Integration of diverse supporting materials Interchangeability of map layers and real-time APIs Availability of spatial analysis tools Inclusion of textual analysis tools A skilfully designed user-friendly box and sidebars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tailored for spatial contexts Questions designed for easy comprehension “Roundless” process Large sample size of users Rapid analysis within short time frames Minimized implementation costs Simplified facilitator role Straightforward acquisition of judgments Respondents can complete the questionnaire over multiple sessions Reduced drop-out rates Simple calculation of opinion convergence metrics Results interpreted clearly and distinctly
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not suitable for textual questions Only one consensus circle per question is available The presence of multiple clusters could interfere with the convergence circle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Same weaknesses of the traditional Delphi method (e.g., sample size, expertise quantification) The presence of small study areas could lead to issues with the final convergence

In our case, the spatial scenarios generated through the collective input of 167 experts offer valuable insights for identifying and proposing novel implementations within specific geographical regions. Thus, in the absence of specific guidelines or quantitative data, effective actions and policies can be applied, or at the very least, anticipated through preliminary results. Indeed, it is important to acknowledge—as explained in the initial sections—that these findings are not absolute and should be augmented with quantitative models (hence our reference to mixed-methods), including comparisons with spatial models when quantitative data are available, and policy assessments. DBSS could potentially represent an innovative frontier for analyzing complex systems or addressing real-world issues, using participatory approaches that incorporate a forward-looking perspective.

To have a complete vision of the method, in our study, we identified an updated list of strengths and weaknesses, categorizing them into two main categories: the first pertaining to technological aspects and the second to methodological aspects. (1) Technological functionality: the Real-Time Geo-Spatial Consensus System, adopted for our purposes, is an effective tool, fully capable of addressing the inputs required in survey creation and expert response acquisition. This platform overcomes the primary weaknesses of the RTSD. Specifically, the administrator can create multiple surveys, enabling investigations in various research contexts. In our exercise, various panelists provided us with feedback (see Calleo and Pilla 2024 for an extensive assessment from the facilitators and panelists), confirming that: “[...] the platform appears to be optimal for decision-making and futures studies, with significant potential for further development.” Furthermore, the ability to create multiple surveys offers the opportunity to involve numerous experts, a task that proves challenging in the conventional version of the Delphi method. This is because the facilitator would need to handle all aspects of information management, including questionnaires, statistical summaries, emails, and

more. From a technical standpoint, it can be affirmed that RT-GSCS, with its user-friendly interface, mitigates high dropout rates during the process. Experts are motivated by the real-time dynamic process, contributing their insights through point allocation, comments, and document readings directly within the platform. Moreover, the inclusion of real-time statistical algorithms that present descriptive statistics, along with features such as heatmap analysis, cluster analysis, and real-time weather data, not only enhances the platform's appeal but also contributes to the effectiveness of the overall method. In this case, some of the weaknesses expressed by Di Zio et al. (2017) are addressed, including the possibility of creating one survey per time, the lack of spatial analysis, and the requirement for programming skills. The employed platform is intentionally designed to be user-friendly, making it straightforward to create surveys, log in, and provide expert judgments. Indeed, based on a survey conducted after the process, the majority of experts rated with a value of 9 on a scale of 1–10 the user-friendly interface, usability, and functionality of the platform (an extended list of strengths and weaknesses is illustrated in Table 4). Nevertheless, some weaknesses related to the technological aspect are still present. As expressed by Di Zio et al. (2017), the platform is not optimized for nonspatial contexts. However, there is a potential avenue for future development where Real-Time Delphi (Gordon and Pease 2006) could be introduced to address textual aspects in such contexts (already available in v3.0 of the platform). Additionally, a notable issue with the platform pertains to the delineation of study area borders. From a local standpoint, the platform performs exceptionally well; however, when observed on a national scale, certain weaknesses become evident. Specifically, when points are widely dispersed and form multiple clusters, achieving convergence within a defined area becomes challenging.

Moreover, even when convergence is achieved within one area, this approach tends to neglect other clusters. In this regard, a revision of the algorithm could prove beneficial, calculating

multiple territorial circles in real-time and based on proximity or distance. Additionally, a notable issue with the platform pertains to the delineation of study area borders. From a local standpoint, the platform performs exceptionally well; however, when observed on a national scale, certain weaknesses become evident. Specifically, when points are widely dispersed and form multiple clusters, achieving convergence within a defined area becomes challenging. Moreover, even when convergence is achieved within one area, this approach tends to neglect other clusters. In this regard, a revision of the algorithm could prove beneficial, calculating multiple territorial circles in real-time and based on proximity or distance. (2) Methodological considerations: from a methodological perspective, the method proved to be robust, able to satisfy the research questions for our large case study. The main strengths of the method can be attributed first to the robustness of the Delphi-based scenario, including the anonymity, iteration (in this case in real-time), controlled feedback, and statistical group responses (Rowe and Wright, 1999). Furthermore, DBSS offers several advantages that are currently absent in traditional DBS. These include its adaptability to spatial contexts, the elimination of distinct rounds and associated costs, the capacity to accommodate a substantial number of panelists, reduced efforts required from the facilitator for statistical analysis, direct integration of materials within the platform, absence of predefined intervals, and a straightforward interpretation of responses. Nevertheless, certain weaknesses continue to exist within the method (in this case, we avoided expressing the weaknesses of the Delphi method already expressed by Calleo et al. 2023). These encompass its lack of adaptability to nonspatial contexts, challenges associated with the influence of multiple clusters on statistical summaries, and the limitation posed by a relatively small study area. In this context, experts might encounter difficulty in attaining precise convergence on specific streets or zones within the city.

4 | Concluding Remarks and Future Works

In this paper, we presented a methodological innovation for the Real-Time Spatial Delphi study, validated with a large-scale case study in the climate change context, developing DBSS for 10 European coastal cities. These scenarios offer a spatial depiction of potential future outcomes and are useful for policy implementation or actions to prevent dystopian future scenarios. Indeed, this study set out to investigate how spatially explicit expert-based methods, specifically the Real-Time Spatial Delphi and the newly introduced concept of Asymptotic Theoretical Consensus, can be used to construct and validate future scenarios related to climate impacts in European coastal cities. By applying the RT-GSCS platform across ten different urban contexts, we were able to assess the plausibility and spatial convergence of expert judgments regarding climate risks in 2050. The data analysis directly supports our central research aim by demonstrating that the proposed approach not only captures spatial consensus effectively but also introduces a robust framework to monitor the dynamics and stability of the consensus-building process. Through comparative cross-city analysis, the findings validate methodological advancement and its practical utility in supporting long-term planning and policy development.

Specifically, in our study, the results fully met the research objectives; it was possible to develop, through the cooperation of 167 experts, 30 DBSS in different contexts and different geographic areas. This paper examines these situations as potential areas of the region where impactful events like coastal erosion, flood risk, threats to biodiversity, and other hazardous weather events might occur. In the results of the spatial analysis, including the heatmaps, a strong plausibility of occurrence emerged, thus leading to the request of immediate actions in the present that involve governmental and local authorities and citizens. Given the absence of a comparative analysis of multiple results from the Real-Time Spatial Delphi in existing literature, this paper demonstrates the dynamic progression specific to each question and territory, highlighting instances where there is a notable consensus among panelists' viewpoints. Indeed, the collaborative process emerged in our study is really significant, and most of the scenarios—which are distinct for each question—can be considered positive because a convergence has been found on the territory. Moreover, with the modeling of the consensus process through the exponential models and introduction of the Asymptotic Theoretical Consensus (ATC) concept, we obtained interesting information on the convergence process over time in terms of duration, smoothness of the convergence, and stability. In the majority of cases, the convergence formation process appeared to be regular. However, in instances where the exponential model did not yield a good fit (low R^2), the issues may be attributed to the territory under examination, where experts have identified multiple plausible zones, giving rise to multiple clusters in the region. This not only poses an issue for the indicators themselves but also for the models used and should be considered in the next studies from a spatial perspective (e.g., dividing the territory into neighborhoods, multiple circles availability). Furthermore, we considered a specific form from the exponential family; however, different models could be performed. In our specific case, by keeping the exponential model, we were able to compare all cases in terms of the convergence process and stability. If a different function were to be sought for each case, it would involve assessing other aspects of the convergence evolution process (e.g., the “shape” of the convergence process or the convergence speed).

For our study, we used the Real-Time Geo-Spatial Consensus System, a novel platform proposed by Calleo et al. (2023), useful for decision-making and forecasting. This platform demonstrates itself to be efficient in our case, permitting the efforts of the facilitator and helping experts to provide judgments without requiring particular computer or GIS skills. The platform, in its current version (v3.0), is provided with different tools, including the possibility to attach materials inside, create multiple questions in different geographic locations, have a dedicated back-end panel, providing researchers a valid tool for administering spatial surveys. Presently, the platform allows for a variety of real-time analyses, encompassing the identification of opinion convergence, real-time cluster analysis, immediate generation of heatmaps, and, more recently, the incorporation of textual analysis using word clouds. However, the approach we identified—alongside the conventional challenges associated with the Delphi method—also revealed certain shortcomings. These include the inability to construct a traditional text-based questionnaire, as well as the absence of multiple circles within

the territory, limiting the discussion to a localized perspective. Additionally, it is evident that the outcomes for smaller areas are impacted, as experts encounter challenges in identifying streets or zones within limited geographical spaces.

To address these challenges, future works could incorporate various enhancements on the platform. This might involve introducing the option to establish diverse geo-consensus circles, enabling a more comprehensive perspective without disregarding specific clusters. Furthermore, novel spatial analyses could also be integrated, such as the incorporation of weighted heatmaps and the inclusion of weighted points within the statistical algorithm. Additionally, within the realm of statistical algorithms, a weighted-points approach is set to be introduced, which entails assigning varying degrees of importance to opinion-points during the convergence process. A prospective improvement could encompass the integration of real-time textual analysis of experts' comments and judgments (e.g., sophisticated textual analysis). This integration would involve and optimizing natural language processing techniques to scrutinize the textual inputs provided by experts throughout the process, through an intuitive interface. Finally, as Artificial Intelligence continues to advance, diverse implementations could be adopted to enhance result analysis. Given the inherent unpredictability of the future, envisioning conclusive outcomes is challenging. One intriguing avenue is the utilization of Generative Adversarial Networks to generate authentic images depicting potential future events (Calleo et al. 2024; Calleo et al. 2025).

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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Appendix

Time Series Models Outputs

See Table A1–A3.

TABLE A1 | First model ($Y = b \cdot \exp(-x \cdot c) + d$).

SC	City	b	c	d	sse	rsquare	dfe	adjrsquare	rmse
1	Benidorm	-36.338	48.829	0.751	1.774	0.000	11.000	-0.182	0.402
2	Benidorm	4653.689	5.996	0.655	0.677	0.542	9.000	0.440	0.274
3	Benidorm	-8.619	15.428	0.982	5.836	0.000	10.000	-0.200	0.764
4	Dublin	9.415	0.157	0.296	68.444	0.722	52.000	0.711	1.147
5	Dublin	-637.985	170.117	1.049	19.295	0.000	27.000	-0.074	0.845
6	Dublin	4.973	3.492	1.353	44.403	0.000	29.000	-0.069	1.237
7	Gdansk	10.078	0.121	-2.035	3.659	0.916	11.000	0.900	0.577
8	Gdansk	10.546	0.145	-1.474	4.467	0.913	11.000	0.897	0.637
9	Gdansk	1.044	4.448	2.546	31.248	0.000	11.000	-0.182	1.685
10	Massa	9.689	0.218	0.531	13.274	0.733	9.000	0.674	1.214
11	Massa	21.657	0.490	0.261	25.497	0.782	8.000	0.728	1.785
12	Massa	80171.632	6.809	0.665	0.776	0.771	7.000	0.706	0.333
13	Oeiras	8.086	1.285	0.490	0.170	0.889	9.000	0.865	0.137
14	Oeiras	6.386	1.307	0.415	0.644	0.481	8.000	0.351	0.284
15	Oeiras	-4.647	5.767	1.057	15.560	0.000	9.000	-0.222	1.315
16	Piran	5.576	0.132	-0.784	2.351	0.909	11.000	0.892	0.462
17	Piran	8.293	0.601	0.359	0.788	0.951	11.000	0.943	0.268
18	Piran	55.482	0.808	0.420	2.983	0.951	15.000	0.944	0.446
19	Samsun	8.325	0.268	-0.233	1.411	0.962	13.000	0.957	0.329
20	Samsun	39861452.100	6.040	0.748	7.674	0.936	13.000	0.927	0.768
21	Samsun	8.302	0.265	0.263	8.461	0.832	12.000	0.804	0.840
22	San Sebastián	45.099	2.398	0.435	0.675	0.663	9.000	0.588	0.274
23	San Sebastián	-8.042	15.908	0.764	2.972	0.000	7.000	-0.286	0.652
24	San Sebastián	1008001.401	8.325	0.480	0.604	0.703	9.000	0.636	0.259
25	Sligo	4507.733	0.000	-4502.238	53.904	0.454	16.000	0.386	1.835
26	Sligo	2.618	0.074	-0.640	0.812	0.821	14.000	0.795	0.241
27	Sligo	-0.058	9.752	2.305	35.629	0.000	15.000	-0.133	1.541
28	Vilanova i la Geltrú	-37.216	49.190	0.958	5.656	0.000	9.000	-0.222	0.793
29	Vilanova i la Geltrú	11.896	1.036	0.563	0.925	0.922	11.000	0.908	0.290
30	Vilanova i la Geltrú	-9.373	17.688	2.057	12.971	0.000	10.000	-0.200	1.139

TABLE A2 | Second model ($Y = b \cdot \exp(-x) + d$).

SC	City	b	d	sse	rsquare	dfe	adjrsquare	rmse
1	Benidorm	1.456	0.708	1.685	0.050	12.000	-0.029	0.375
2	Benidorm	3.883	0.614	0.665	0.549	10.000	0.504	0.258
3	Benidorm	32.381	0.657	2.098	0.640	11.000	0.608	0.437
4	Dublin	56.953	2.436	147.155	0.402	53.000	0.391	1.666

(Continues)

TABLE A2 | (Continued)

SC	City	b	d	sse	rsquare	dfe	adjrsquare	rmse
5	Dublin	11.464	0.653	5.251	0.728	28.000	0.718	0.433
6	Dublin	72.862	1.251	42.209	0.049	30.000	0.018	1.186
7	Gdansk	50.187	1.943	19.004	0.562	12.000	0.526	1.258
8	Gdansk	60.677	1.850	15.247	0.703	12.000	0.678	1.127
9	Gdansk	11.139	2.337	26.488	0.152	12.000	0.082	1.486
10	Massa	24.918	2.844	26.730	0.463	10.000	0.410	1.635
11	Massa	39.876	1.759	39.639	0.661	9.000	0.624	2.099
12	Massa	8.308	0.625	0.838	0.753	8.000	0.722	0.324
13	Oeiras	5.382	0.465	0.176	0.885	10.000	0.874	0.133
14	Oeiras	3.797	0.399	0.657	0.470	9.000	0.412	0.270
15	Oeiras	52.116	0.387	2.573	0.835	10.000	0.818	0.507
16	Piran	14.228	1.108	11.062	0.572	12.000	0.536	0.960
17	Piran	15.845	0.547	1.275	0.921	12.000	0.915	0.326
18	Piran	92.930	0.527	3.524	0.942	16.000	0.938	0.469
19	Samsun	23.047	1.166	11.168	0.703	14.000	0.682	0.893
20	Samsun	87.193	0.398	20.524	0.830	14.000	0.818	1.211
21	Samsun	23.482	1.515	15.605	0.691	13.000	0.667	1.096
22	San Sebastián	4.520	0.392	0.743	0.629	10.000	0.592	0.273
23	San Sebastián	19.453	0.518	0.645	0.783	8.000	0.756	0.284
24	San Sebastián	4.790	0.437	0.726	0.642	10.000	0.606	0.270
25	Sligo	38.702	3.414	83.642	0.153	17.000	0.103	2.218
26	Sligo	5.586	0.649	2.060	0.546	15.000	0.516	0.371
27	Sligo	15.587	2.052	25.800	0.276	16.000	0.231	1.270
28	Vilanova i la Geltrú	10.774	0.657	1.045	0.815	10.000	0.797	0.323
29	Vilanova i la Geltrú	11.296	0.550	0.927	0.922	12.000	0.915	0.278
30	Vilanova i la Geltrú	9.707	1.745	9.074	0.300	11.000	0.237	0.908

TABLE A3 | Third model ($Y = b \cdot \exp(-x \cdot c)$).

SC	City	b	c	sse	rsquare	dfe	adjrsquare	rmse
1	Benidorm	1.154	0.072	1.331	0.250	12.000	0.187	0.333
2	Benidorm	1.538	0.130	0.659	0.554	10.000	0.509	0.257
3	Benidorm	5.335	0.306	1.640	0.719	11.000	0.693	0.386
4	Dublin	9.475	0.144	68.950	0.720	53.000	0.714	1.141
5	Dublin	3.718	0.244	0.960	0.950	28.000	0.948	0.185
6	Dublin	3.349	0.061	30.484	0.313	30.000	0.291	1.008
7	Gdansk	9.401	0.210	4.474	0.897	12.000	0.888	0.611
8	Gdansk	10.392	0.219	4.944	0.904	12.000	0.896	0.642
9	Gdansk	6.720	0.149	9.979	0.681	12.000	0.654	0.912
10	Massa	9.653	0.183	13.393	0.731	10.000	0.704	1.157
11	Massa	21.348	0.464	25.664	0.781	9.000	0.756	1.689
12	Massa	2.099	0.150	2.357	0.306	8.000	0.219	0.543

(Continues)

TABLE A3 | (Continued)

SC	City	b	c	sse	rsquare	dfc	adjrsquare	rmse
13	Oeiras	1.941	0.237	0.675	0.560	10.000	0.516	0.260
14	Oeiras	0.935	0.096	0.984	0.206	9.000	0.118	0.331
15	Oeiras	23.989	0.686	2.779	0.821	10.000	0.804	0.527
16	Piran	5.251	0.197	2.611	0.899	12.000	0.891	0.466
17	Piran	6.306	0.395	1.167	0.928	12.000	0.922	0.312
18	Piran	37.118	0.640	4.716	0.922	16.000	0.917	0.543
19	Samsun	8.491	0.300	1.470	0.961	14.000	0.958	0.324
20	Samsun	6008.685	2.589	14.461	0.880	14.000	0.872	1.016
21	Samsun	8.144	0.233	8.507	0.831	13.000	0.818	0.809
22	San Sebastián	1.482	0.183	0.846	0.578	10.000	0.535	0.291
23	San Sebastián	3.636	0.257	0.071	0.976	8.000	0.973	0.094
24	San Sebastián	1.558	0.171	0.789	0.611	10.000	0.572	0.281
25	Sligo	10.195	0.125	39.664	0.598	17.000	0.575	1.527
26	Sligo	2.139	0.130	0.839	0.815	15.000	0.803	0.237
27	Sligo	6.669	0.156	9.936	0.721	16.000	0.704	0.788
28	Vilanova i la Geltrú	3.804	0.272	0.766	0.865	10.000	0.851	0.277
29	Vilanova i la Geltrú	6.196	0.499	2.103	0.822	12.000	0.807	0.419
30	Vilanova i la Geltrú	4.058	0.113	4.034	0.689	11.000	0.661	0.606